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Frequency stabilization of a sophisticated multi-area interconnected hybrid power system considering non-inertia sources

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ABSTRACT

This study introduces a novel interconnected power system model, which combines four real areas, integrating conventional power plants with renewable energy sources (RESs). This comprehensive system model aims to address the load frequency control (LFC) challenges that such systems face. Where the integration of RESs into power systems poses significant challenges, particularly in maintaining frequency stability. The LFC approach utilizes a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller, meticulously optimized through the Runge-Kutta (RUN) optimizer based on its mathematical principles. Dealing with the uncertainties of RESs and system nonlinearities poses a significant challenge for this controller. The efficacy of the proposed PID controller based on the RUN algorithm is examined by analyzing the frequency stability of the Egyptian power system (EPS), which stays interconnected with neighboring grids in Jordan, Libya, and Sudan. This study accounts for various loading scenarios and system nonlinearities to validate the algorithm's effectiveness. Furthermore, the superior performance of the RUN optimizer is verified by contrasting its results with other widely recognized optimization techniques, such as the Ant Lion optimizer (ALO) and Chernobyl disaster optimizer (CDO). Additionally, the PID controller based on the RUN optimizer is also evaluated against literature that employed a moth swarm algorithm (MSA) to design the PID controller-based LFC in the EPS. Simulation results in the MATLAB environment demonstrate the effectiveness and robustness of the proposed PID controller based on the RUN algorithm. The RUN-based PID controller outperforms other PID controllers optimized using algorithms from the literature (e.g., ALO, CDO, and MSA), achieving superior performance across various contingencies, including load variations, RES uncertainties, and system nonlinearities. The results highlight the effectiveness of the proposed controller compared to those in the literature, improving the maximum overshoot by approximately 20% and reducing the minimum undershoot by about 30%. As a result, the system reaches steady-state conditions roughly 15 s faster. Finally, to leverage the precision of physical simulation and the flexibility of numerical simulation, the proposed PID controller, based on the RUN algorithm, is validated and implemented in a real-time environment using the OPA-RT platform.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The global adoption of renewable energy sources (RESs) for electricity generation is experiencing sustained and rapid growth. This widespread adoption is driven by a range of interconnected factors, including technological advancements, environmental considerations,

and economic incentives. These include the motivation to enhance energy security through diversified sources, reduce reliance on foreign fuel imports, address environmental concerns, and prepare for anticipated fossil fuel depletion. Numerous technologies exist for producing power from renewable resources [1]. However, due to its greater maturity and lower prices compared to other renewable technologies like geothermal, biomass, etc., electricity generated by wind and solar power is the most commonly used. All country's power systems have included conventional generating for the past few decades, such as hydropower and

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Nomenclature			
<i>EPS</i>	Egyptian power system	D_{LPS}	Damping coefficient of a Libyan power system in (pu MW/Hz)
<i>JPS</i>	Jordan power system	<i>P.F.8</i>	Non-reheat thermal power plants participation factor of LPS
<i>LBS</i>	Libya power system	<i>P.F.9</i>	Reheat thermal power plants participation factor of LPS
<i>SBS</i>	Sudan power system	R_8	Governor speed regulation of non-reheat thermal power plants of LPS (Hz/ pu MW)
<i>RESs</i>	Renewable Energy Sources	R_9	Thermal speed regulation of the governor (reheat) of LPS (Hz/ pu MW)
<i>PV</i>	Photovoltaic	H_{SPS}	Inertia constant (s) of SPS
<i>LFC</i>	Load Frequency Control	D_{SPS}	Damping coefficient of SPS in (pu MW/Hz)
<i>PID</i>	Proportional Integral Derivative controller	<i>P.F.10</i>	Participation factor of non-reheat thermal power plants of SPS
<i>RUN</i>	Runge Kutta optimizer	<i>P.F.11</i>	Participation factor of reheat thermal power plants of SPS
<i>CDO</i>	Chernobyl disaster optimizer	R_{10}	Governor speed regulation of non-reheat thermal power plants of SPS (Hz/ pu MW)
<i>ALO</i>	Ant Lion optimizer	R_{11}	Thermal speed regulation of the governor (reheat) of SPS (Hz/ pu MW)
<i>ITAE</i>	Integral of Time-weighted Absolute Error	T_{t1}	Thermal turbine time constant (non-reheat) (s)
H_{EPS}	Inertia constant (s) of Egyptian power system area	T_{g1}	Thermal governor time constant (non-reheat) (s)
D_{EPS}	Damping coefficient (load frequency characteristic) in (pu MW/Hz) of Egypt area	T_{t2}	Thermal turbine time constant (reheat) (s)
<i>P.F.1</i>	Non-reheat thermal power plants participation factor of EPS	T_{g2}	Thermal governor time constant (reheat) (s)
<i>P.F.2</i>	Reheat thermal power plants participation factor of EPS	T_{g3}	Governor main servo time constant of hydro power plants (s)
<i>P.F.3</i>	Hydropower power plants participation factor of EPS	T_3	Governor transient droop time constant of hydropower plants (s)
R_1	Thermal speed regulation of the governor (non-reheat) of EPS (Hz/ pu MW)	K_{r2}	Reheat thermal power plants reheater gain
R_2	Thermal speed regulation of the governor (reheat) of EPS (Hz/ pu MW)	K_{PV}	Photovoltaic generation gain
R_3	Hydraulic speed governor regulation of EPS (Hz/ pu MW)	K_{WG}	Wind speed governor gain
H_{JPS}	Jordan power system inertia constant (s)	T_d	Governor reset time constant of hydropower plants (s)
D_{JPS}	Jordan power system damping coefficient (pu MW/Hz)	T_w	Water starting time in penstock of hydropower plants (s)
<i>P.F.4</i>	Non-reheat thermal power plants participation factor of JPS	T_{r2}	Reheat time constant of reheat thermal power plants (s)
<i>P.F.5</i>	Reheat thermal power plants participation factor of JPS	P_w	Wind power generation output power
<i>P.F.6</i>	Hydropower power plants Participation factor of JPS	β	The pitch angle (degree)
<i>P.F.7</i>	Diesel power plants participation factor of JPS	ρ	Air density (Kg/m ³)
R_4	Thermal speed regulation of the governor (non-reheat) of JPS (Hz/ pu MW)	r_T	Radius of the rotor (m)
R_5	Thermal speed regulation of the governor (reheat) of JPS (Hz/ pu MW)	A_T	Rotor swept area (m ²)
R_6	Hydraulic speed governor regulation of JPS (Hz/ pu MW)	V_w	Rated wind speed (m/s),
R_7	Governor speed regulation of diesel power plants of JPS (Hz/ pu MW)	δ	The rotor angle (degree)
H_{LPS}	Inertia constant (s) of Libyan power system	C_p	Power coefficient of the rotor blades
		$C_{1..7}$	Turbine coefficients

thermal power plants which are fueled primarily by natural gas and oil, with a limited contribution from RESs. To strengthen energy security and reduce reliance on fuel imports, nations strive to diversify their electricity generation mix. In addition, they set targets to increase the share of RESs in their overall power generation capacity, aiming to meet recommended benchmarks. Hydropower, wind power, and photovoltaic (PV) solar power plants are among the RESs that have been installed. Globally, there has been a rapid expansion in both the installed generation capacity and the variety of energy sources utilized. The expansion in capacity and the shift to a higher percentage of RESs in the mix of power generated could complicate and tiresomely operate systems. The intermittent nature of RESs poses significant challenges in maintaining a stable balance between electricity generation and consumption, leading to frequency fluctuations within the power system. Sharing large amounts of (RENS) needs load frequency control (LFC) to ensure power system stability. As a result, extensive research and studies are necessary to operate and control future networks effectively.

1.2. Literature review

The LFC of power systems with high penetration of RESs is one of the

major issues that has drawn a lot of attention from researchers. The LFC's objective is to control fluctuating load demands and system disturbances by keeping each area's frequency and inter-area tie-line power within allowable ranges [2]. Multiple studies have investigated the aspect of frequency control in different power systems, ranging from microgrids to large-scale power systems, taking into consideration various RESs. The LFC in multi-area deregulated environments with penetrations of RESs like solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind power has been included along with its intermittent nature as well as nonlinearities such as generation rate constant (GRC) and governor deadband (GDB) have been taken into consideration are deeply introduced in [3]. Frequency and tie-line power flow stabilization in a multi-microgrid system using fractional order-based integral derivative and proportional integral derivative with filter is presented in [4]. For instance, researchers in [5] examined two-area interconnected power system behavior using LFC that incorporated both wind and PV generation. The authors of [6] considered a two-area interconnected hybrid power system including a thermal plant, hydro plant, and gas plant in each area. Moreover, both control areas also incorporate sporadic solar and wind power plants as well as electric vehicles for improving the LFC mechanisms. Furthermore, the authors of [7] investigated the frequency stability concern of a

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of a four-area interconnected multi-source power system under investigation.

three-area interconnected power system considering wind and concentrated solar thermal power plants.

Frequency and tie-line power variations in a multi-area restructured power system are addressed under various conditions, such as load fluctuations, wind speed variations, solar irradiation, GDB, and GRC. This system was also analyzed with the integration of energy storage systems (ESSs) taking into consideration the unexpected nature of wind speed and solar irradiation [8]. The reliability of electrical power systems with hybrid power plants including thermal power plants, RESs (such as wind, parabolic trough solar thermal plant, biogas), and electric vehicle assets is tested to ensure frequency stability with demand response strategy to reduce peak demand [9]. Moreover, the impact of electric vehicles in frequency regulation of deregulated environment power systems, which include hydro, thermal, and gas turbine units as well as RESs (i.e., solar, wind, and geothermal energy) is presented in [10]. For suppressing the variations of frequency and of tie-line power flow due to the intermittent nature of RESs and frequently varying load demands, a double-stage controller incorporating a three-degree-of-freedom (3-DOF) fractional-order proportional-integral (FOPI) controller and FO proportional-derivative (FOPD) controller, referred to 3-DOF (FOPI)-FOPD controller, has been used in [11].

The frequency stability issue of an islanded microgrid comprising generation from wind and PV is addressed and analyzed in [12]. Standalone microgrids experience lower inertia and lack primary frequency control that requires such tidal turbines to liberate their accumulated kinetic energy in rotational parts pursuing frequency fluctuations due to unpredictable renewable sources [13]. On the other side, several studies looked into the use of numerous ESSs to enhance the frequency stability of power systems, hence overcoming the large frequency/voltage deviations caused by RESs uncertainties. These energy storage technologies have comprised flywheels [14], batteries [15], pumped hydro [16], supercapacitors [17], and superconducting magnetic energy storage [18], among others. The authors of [19] discuss the

effect of using battery ESS and electric vehicles in LFC of a multi-microgrid with a hybrid system consisting of a wind turbine generator, solar PV, diesel engine generator, aquea electrolyzer, and fuel cell. Moreover, capacitive ESS units are incorporated with a multi-source interconnected two-area thermal-hydro-gas power system to compensate for the fluctuations in the frequency by the load disturbances mismatch between the supplied and demanded powers [20]. The results of multiple investigations demonstrated the potential contribution that ESSs could make to the frequency regulation of different power systems that are integrated with a large number of RESs. However, the widespread use of large power systems is hampered by their high cost.

1.3. Research gap and motivation

The literature review indicates that the LFC is primarily influenced by the advanced methodologies employed in determining the controller parameters. Many control Techniques/strategies have been used in recent decades for the LFC of modern power systems, including robust control [21], linear quadratic regulator [22], variable structure control [23], and model predictive control [24]. Although these control techniques/strategies are efficient in handling the power systems' nonlinear characteristics, they occasionally struggle to determine the controller parameters [25]. Therefore, numerous studies have used artificial intelligence techniques like fuzzy logic controllers [26] and artificial neural networks [27]. However, it suffers from the long training time, the number of neurons in each layer, and the selecting number of layers are the drawbacks. Furthermore, the fuzzy logic controller needs to work hard to detect effective signals, and it requires fine-tuning and simulation before operation.

Another approach, utilizing several optimization techniques to handle the LFC problem as these algorithms are capable of treating nonlinear objective functions. Consequently, a variety of optimization techniques have been used to determine the frequency controllers'

Fig. 2. Dynamic model of the EPS considering RESs.

Table 1

Installed generation capacity of multiple power plants in Egypt from 2016 to 2021 [36].

Power plant (GW)	Year		2018/2019	2019/2020	2020/2021
	2016/2017	2017/2018			
Combined Cycle	12.630	30.030	32.470	32.448	32.448
Steam Units	15.449	15.449	16.749	17.179	17.179
Gas Turbines	13.345	5.745	4.055	4.055	3.343
Hydropower	2.800	2.832	2.832	2.832	2.832
Renewables	0.887	1.157	2.274	3.016	3.016

Table 2

The EPS nominal parameters [24,34].

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
H_{EPS}	8.140	T_{g1}	0.080
D_{EPS}	0.028	T_{i1}	0.300
K_{r2}	0.500	T_{g2}	0.080
K_{PV}	1.000	T_{i2}	0.300
K_{WG}	1.000	T_{r2}	10.000
$P.F.1$	0.02529	T_{g3}	0.200
$P.F.2$	0.6107	T_3	90
$P.F.3$	0.1364	T_d	5.000
R_1	2.500	T_w	1.000
R_2	2.500	T_{PV}	1.850
R_3	1.000	T_{WG}	1.500

parameters, including genetic algorithm [28], particle swarm optimization [29], bacteria foraging [30], artificial bee colony [31], ant colony optimization [32], and others. While these algorithms demonstrate effectiveness in addressing the design problem, they exhibit limitations such as weak local search capabilities and slow convergence during the refinement stage. These issues may lead to the algorithms becoming trapped in local minimum solutions. Consequently, a new evolutionary computation algorithm, titled the cuckoo search algorithm has been introduced and further designed newly by [33].

Furthermore, RESs' intermittent nature, results from several control difficulties in power systems. The integration of RESs into power systems involves the utilization of power electronic converters which lack inertia characteristics, resulting in a decline of the total power system inertia. Reduced power system inertia can lead to a high rate of change of frequency (RoCoF) and frequency fluctuations, which may cause power system instability. RoCoF is lowered by the inertia of the dynamically rotating mass, such as motors as well as generators. Using virtual synchronous generators (VSG) is one suggested solution to this problem [34]. With VSG, the ESSs or RESs' power electronic devices are managed to mimic the features of synchronous generators and offer inertia and damping qualities that lower the RoCoF, decrease frequency deviations following disturbances consequently improve frequency stability.

1.4. Contribution

Motivated by the observations outlined above, this paper investigates the frequency stability of a realistic four-area interconnected multi-source power system, comprising Egypt, Jordan, Sudan, and Libya, with a focus on the integration of RESs. PID controllers are widely utilized across various industries, including LFC applications in power

Fig. 3. Dynamic model of the JPS considering RESs.

Table 3
Installed generation capacity in Jordan from 2017 to 2022 [37].

Power plant (GW)	Year				
	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	2020/2021	2021/2022
Combined Cycle	2.740	2.740	2.740	2.740	2.740
Steam Units	0.605	0.605	0.363	0.363	0.598
Gas Turbines	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.060	0.060
Diesel	0.814	0.814	0.814	0.814	0.814
Hydro	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.004
Wind	0.280	0.369	0.518	0.622	0.622
Solar	0.449	0.637	0.887	0.938	0.958

systems, due to their simplicity and proven effectiveness in enhancing system performance. Therefore, this study proposes an efficient LFC strategy based on an optimal PID controller for every area of the realistic interconnected power system. For improved performance, PID controller parameters need to be carefully adjusted, which requires significant effort for various frequency controllers in interconnected power systems. The effectiveness and efficiency of the proposed PID controllers' optimal design are achieved through the utilization of the Runge Kutta (RUN) optimizer based on the mathematical principles and concepts of the Runge Kutta method widely well-known in mathematics [35]. The outstanding performance of the RUN optimizer is verified by contrasting it against established optimization algorithms, including the

Table 4
JPS nominal parameters.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
H_{JPS}	4.640	R_6	1
D_{JPS}	0.028	R_7	1
K_{r2}	0.500	T_{g1}	0.080
K_{PV}	1.000	T_{l1}	0.300
K_{WG}	1.000	T_{g2}	0.080
$P.F.4$	0.0906	T_{g4}	0.01
$P.F.5$	0.684	T_{l2}	0.300
$P.F.6$	0.0016	T_{l3}	5.00
$P.F.7$	0.203	T_{r2}	10.000
R_4	2.500	T_{PV}	1.850
R_5	2.500	T_{WG}	1.500

Table 5
LPS nominal parameters.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
H_{LPS}	6.690	R_9	2.500
D_{LPS}	0.028	T_{g1}	0.080
K_{r2}	0.500	T_{l1}	0.300
$P.F.8$	0.63	T_{g2}	0.080
$P.F.9$	0.37	T_{l2}	0.300
R_8	2.500	T_{r2}	10.000

Fig. 4. LPS Dynamic model.

Fig. 5. Dynamic model of the SPS.

Table 6
SPS nominal parameters.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
H_{SPS}	4.540	R_{11}	2.500
D_{SPS}	0.028	T_{g1}	0.080
K_{r2}	0.500	T_{g3}	0.200
P.F.10	0.63	T_d	0.080
P.F.11	0.37	T_3	90.00
R_{10}	2.500	T_w	1.000

Ant Lion optimizer (ALO) and Chernobyl disaster optimizer (CDO). These comparisons were conducted to address diverse challenges encountered in optimization problems discussed within literature. The goal behind this research is to confirm and demonstrate the reliability of the recommended PID controller based on the proposed RUN optimization technique for frequency control of the studied four-area interconnected multi-source power system. Also, the proposed PID controller, utilizing the RUN algorithm, is assessed for applicability and effectiveness in a real-time environment using the OPAL-RT platform. Hence, enhancing the performance of frequency stability of realistic

interconnected renewable power systems considering system nonlinearities.

1.5. Paper organization

The outstanding sections of this research are arranged in the following way: Section 2 presents the dynamic model of a realistic four-area interconnected multi-source power system. Section 3 illustrates the proposed PID controller for the LFC of the studied power system. Section 4 presents the RUN optimizer. The performance assessment of the proposed system including the stability analysis of the proposed control system is provided in Section 5. Section 6 presents the simulation results along with the real-time implementation. Finally, Section 7 is the paper's conclusion.

2. System configuration

This study presents a novel approach using a realistic model of a four-area interconnected power system, incorporating authentic data besides current connections. It significantly enhances our comprehension of how large nations can establish a reliable power system through

Fig. 6. A model of the solar PV power using MATLAB/SIMULINK.

Fig. 7. Wind power generation model using MATLAB/Simulink.

Table 7
Typical variables of wind turbine [42].

Variable	Value	Variable	Value
PW	3000 kW	Vw	12 m/sec
ρ	1.225 Kg m ²	nT	22.5 rpm
rT	43.36 m	AT	5905 m ²
C1	0.3915	C2	116.0
C3	0.40	C4	0.00
C5	5.00	C6	21.0
C7	0.0192		

interconnections. The primary benefit of this strategy lies in the ability to postpone the construction of new power plants. By using tie-lines to share power across linked grids, this can be accomplished without compromising the security or dependability of the individual grids. Additionally, by reducing the requirement for standby capacity to handle variations in demand, the interconnection lowers operating costs. It makes it possible to build new power plants where they will have the greatest economic appeal, usually near cheap fuel sources.

The studied real power system includes interconnecting the Egyptian power system (EPS) with the Jordanian power system (JPS), the Libyan power system (LPS), and the Sudanese power system (SPS). In 2008, the Egypt-Libya overhead transmission line, which has a capacity of 240 MW and operates at a voltage of 220 kV, was successfully commissioned. During the same year, the Egypt-Jordan link, consisting of a marine cable, became operational. It has a capacity of 300 MW, with the Egyptian side operating at 500 kV –via 500/400 kV power transformer– and the Jordanian side at 400 kV. Additionally, in 2020, the SPS began receiving power from the EPS via two 220 kV circuits. These circuits have a combined capacity of up to 80 MW. Fig. 1 shows the schematic diagram of the four-area interconnected multi-source power system under study. The following subsections describe each of the power systems studied.

2.1. Egyptian power system

The EPS is the largest among all the interconnected power systems examined, with a capacity exceeding 58 GW. The EPS comprises various types of power generation plants operating at different voltage levels, including 500 kV, 220 kV, and 66 kV. The Aswan High Dam, along with Aswan Dams 1 and 2, constitutes the primary hydropower plants within

Fig. 8. The PID controller structure for a single-area power system.

the EPS. These hydropower plants play a crucial role in the LFC due to their rapid response in mitigating frequency deviations. On the other hand, thermal (conventional) power plants that run using natural gas, coal, or oil constitute the majority of the EPS’s generation capacity. Their high inertia plays a key role in maintaining system stability. Fig. 2 exhibits the dynamic model of the multi-source EPS. Furthermore, the advantages of RESs e.g., solar PV and wind power plants, in terms of the environment, economy, and energy independence are becoming more and more apparent. The EPS includes several renewable power plants, such as the Benban Solar Park in Aswan, and the Gabel El-Zeit and Zafarana wind farms, strategically located across Egypt [36]. The installed generation capacity in Egypt is demonstrated in Table 1, and Table 2 identifies the parameters of the EPS.

2.2. Jordan power system

The JPS comprises the main power generation stations and transmission networks that feed its power system with different voltage levels (400/132/33 kV). These high-voltage transmission lines connect the generation stations to the load centers located in different regions across the Hashemite Kingdom. The JPS has a small, semi-isolated, and

Fig. 9. Flowchart of the RUN optimization algorithm.

conventional-based electrical system [37], everywhere the dynamic model of the JPS is depicted in Fig. 3. Electrical energy in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan is generated primarily from thermal power plants, accounting for 73 % of the total generation, which includes combined cycle, steam units, gas turbines, and diesel generators. Renewable energy contributes 26 %, while the remaining 1 % is derived from hydropower plants and other sources [37]. The installed generation capacity in Jordan is shown in Table 3, and Table 4 identifies the nominal parameters of the JPS.

2.3. Libya power system

Libya, a major oil-producing country in Africa, primarily relies on gas and oil as the main fuels for generating electricity to meet domestic

demand in the national power grid. As a result, thermal power plants form the backbone of electricity generation in Libya. As of 2022, the total installed power generation capacity in Libya is estimated to be around 7.5 to 8 GW. Of this capacity, approximately 43 % is generated by open-cycle gas turbine units, while 37 % comes from combined-cycle gas turbine plants. The remaining portion consists of steam turbine units [38]. Table 5 represents the LPS's nominal parameters and Fig. 4 shows its dynamic model.

2.4. Sudan power system

Sudan is one of the rich countries in water resources, primarily from the Nile River. The country has been heavily dependent on hydropower to meet its electricity demands. As of 2020, Sudan's entire installed

Table 8
Optimal PID controller parameters based on different optimization algorithms.

Power System	PID Controller Parameter	ALO	CDO	Proposed RUN
Area 1 (EPS)	K_p	70.3310	99.9812	100
	K_i	46.2083	43.5907	40.1466
	K_d	73.8306	52.8543	53.1741
Area 2 (JPS)	K_{p1}	99.9240	53.1614	99.9777
	K_{i1}	0.7130	63.9433	20.2758
	K_{d1}	24.6276	92.7812	99.7486
Area 3 (LPS)	K_{p2}	99.9314	99.9954	17.5938
	K_{i2}	74.7726	67.7484	0.4637
	K_{d2}	97.4800	93.9170	98.0717
Area 4 (SPS)	K_{p3}	99.2815	99.9729	16.5780
	K_{i3}	96.0537	99.6426	0.4578
	K_{d3}	47.1200	99.8079	98.2275
ITAE		0.5089	0.06065	0.0542

power production capacity stood at 2,125 MW, of which hydropower accounted for approximately 52 % of the country’s total electricity generation capacity. The major hydropower capacity in Sudan is the 1,250 MW Merowe (Hamdab) power plant, which is located on the Nile River approximately 350 km north of the capital city of Khartoum. Additionally, the country has 360 MW Kajbar Dam. Around 45 % of Sudan’s remaining power generation capacity comes from thermal power plants that utilize liquid fuels such as heavy fuel oil and diesel. Renewable energy sources currently make up a small percentage, estimated at around 3 %, of Sudan’s total electricity generation capacity [39]. The dynamic model SPS appears in Fig. 5. The transmission capacity of the EPS-SPS interconnection tie-line will reach 300 MW by installing two static synchronous compensators (STATCOM) at Merwo and Dongola substations in Sudan with a capacity of 150 MVAR. Table 6 defines the nominal parameters of the SPS.

This research uses MATLAB/SIMULINK to model the four linked power network areas, including all types of electricity generation sources. Since RESs are often associated with the grid via power electronic converters, they are typically non-dispatchable generation sources as well as they have little to no inertia. This means RESs cannot actively participate in frequency regulation during normal grid operations. Considering the challenges posed by the significant proportion of RESs modeled in the EPS and JPS, this presents difficulties for power system control and operation. However, in the SPS, the percentage of RENs is small enough to be neglected in this particular study. The impact

of RESs in the SPS will be considered in future work. Studies on the penetration levels of different renewable energy sources have revealed a significant lot of discussion on the influence of the percentage of renewable energy sources on the frequency stability of power systems. The power plants used in the representation of the investigated real four-area interconnected power system are detailed in the subsections below.

A. Non-reheat thermal power plants

The dynamic model of a non-reheat thermal power plant is denoted in Eq. (1), that gets provided by [40].

$$\Delta P_{m1} = \frac{1}{T_{g1}s + 1} * \frac{1}{T_{r1}s + 1} \left(\frac{-1}{R_1} * \Delta f - \Delta P_{c1} \right) \tag{1}$$

where, ΔP_{m1} , T_{g1} , T_{r1} , R_1 , and ΔP_{c1} stand for the mechanical power change, the time constant of the governor, the time constant of the turbine, the governor’s speed regulation, and control signal from the secondary controller to the non-reheat thermal power plants, respectively. Additionally, s is a complex number ($s = \sigma + j\omega$) and Δf is the system frequency deviation.

B. Reheat thermal power plants

The reheat thermal power plants dynamic model is represented in Eq. (2), which is given by [40].

$$\Delta P_{m3} = \frac{T_d s + 1}{T_3 s + 1} * \left(\frac{1 - T_w s}{1 + 0.5 T_w s} \right) * \left(\frac{-1}{R_3} * \Delta f - \Delta P_{c3} \right) \tag{2}$$

where, ΔP_{m3} , T_{g2} , T_{r2} , T_{r2} , K_{r2} , R_2 , and ΔP_{c2} indicate the power change of the reheat thermal power plants, the time constant of the governor, the time constant of the turbine, the time constant of the reheater, the gain of the reheater, the governor’s speed regulation, and the control signal received from the secondary controller, in that order.

C. Hydropower plants

Equation (3) represents the dynamic model of hydropower plants which is assumed by [41].

$$\Delta P_{m3} = \frac{T_d s + 1}{T_3 s + 1} * \left(\frac{1 - T_w s}{1 + 0.5 T_w s} \right) * \left(\frac{-1}{R_3} * \Delta f - \Delta P_{c3} \right) \tag{3}$$

where, ΔP_{m3} , R_3 , and ΔP_{c3} represent the power change of the hydro-power plants, the governor speed regulation, and the control signal from the secondary controller to hydropower plants, respectively. In addition, T_3 , T_d , are time constants of hydropower plant water gate and speed governor dashpot, and T_w is water starting time in hydro intake.

D. Solar PV power plants

Fig. 10. Convergence curve of the PID controller based on different optimization techniques.

Fig. 11. The frequency deviation of the EPS with PID controller based on different optimization algorithms.

Fig. 12. A simplified block diagram of a closed-loop multi-area power system.

Solar energy is one of the most attractive RESs in the world. Nowadays it is predicted to become the dominant RES in Egypt due to the significant solar irradiance in all seasons and huge open desert places suitable for installing PV power station projects. Presently, Egypt and Jordan produce an adequate level of solar PV power generation, with plans to generate ever-increasing amounts. Equation (4) represents, the dynamic model of PV power generation, which is given by [42].

$$\Delta P_{PV} = \left(\frac{K_{PV}}{T_{PV}s + 1} \right) * \Delta P_{Solar} \quad (4)$$

where K_{PV} and T_{PV} stand for PV generation gain, time constant consequently. ΔP_{PV} denotes the power change of PV generation and ΔP_{Solar} is the power change of solar irradiance [43]. The dynamic model solar PV system is demonstrated in Fig. 6. Due to the variety of weather conditions (temperature and solar irradiation), the output power of the PV is difficult to predict [44]. Consequently, these non-dispatchable generators cause disturbance and fluctuation in the power system under evaluation. Moreover, PV power plants are connected to the power grid through a power electronic-based converter, so these power resources have no inertia. Subsequently, it eliminates the inertia of the overall power system and hence increases system frequency deviations [45].

E. Wind power plants

Wind power is also considered a major promising RESs worldwide.

Like many other countries, Egypt possesses suitable locations for wind power generation projects, primarily in the Gulf of Suez, select sites near the Nile River, areas in Sinai, and regions in the New Valley Governorate [46]. Similarly, Jordan has favorable weather conditions and locations for such initiatives [47]. This investigation represents the dynamic model of wind power generation as in Eq. (5).

$$\Delta P_{WG} = \left(\frac{K_{WG}}{T_{WG}s + 1} \right) * \Delta P_{Wind} \quad (5)$$

where ΔP_{Wind} denotes the power change of wind, K_{WG} stands the gain of wind generation, ΔP_{WG} represents the power change of wind generation, and T_{WG} is the time constant of wind generation. Similar to PV generation and due to wind speed variation along with weather conditions the output power of wind generation is variable and difficult to predict. So, generally, these non-dispatchable generation resources cause power system disturbance as well as fluctuation. The dynamic model wind power plant is shown in Fig. 7. Furthermore, wind power generation is typically linked to the electrical network via a power electronic-based converter, so it supports very little inertia to the power system. Consequently, it eliminates the overall power system inertia especially in case of large frequency deviation with high penetration of the wind power. Table 7 illustrates the nominal wind turbine parameters.

3. Proposed control system

Because of its great performance and ease of use, PID controllers are widely employed in the industry. Based on the particular application, one or more control loops (For instance, proportional (P), integral (I), derivative (D), or proportional-integral (PI) control, etc) may be employed to optimize the controller's performance [48]. In power system control centers, PID controllers continue to be widely used for LFC applications. The PID controller structure can be seen in Fig. 8, and its transfer function is presented in Eq. (6).

$$G_{PID}(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} + K_d s \quad (6)$$

where K_p , K_i and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains respectively, and $G_{PID}(s)$ is the PID controller transfer function. In single-area power systems frequency deviation is identified as the controller

Fig. 13. Bode-plots for the stability of the proposed system, considering the loop-transfer function, are shown as follows: a) EPS, b) JPS, c) LPS, d) SPS.

Fig. 14. Sudden load change applied for area 1(EPS) & area 2 (JPS) Under Case A of Scenario 1.

input; for multi-area power systems area control error (ACE) while the control signal to the power plant is the controller output. The three PID controller gains (i.e., K_p , K_i , and K_d) must be tuned carefully to achieve optimal performance. Therefore, in this study, the PID controller is optimally constructed utilizing an efficient optimization technique based on the mathematical principles and concepts of the Runge Kutta method commonly well-known in mathematics. Moreover, the RUN optimizer is checked and verified by identifying the obtained parameters

of the PID controllers.

This paper implements the RUN algorithm within the MATLAB programming environment. The selection of an appropriate optimization method is crucial for ensuring frequency stability in interconnected power systems under fluctuating load conditions. The objective functions that may be used for such optimization problems include the integral of time-weighted absolute error (ITAE), the integral of absolute error (IAE), the integral of time-weighted squared error (ITSE), and the

Fig. 15. Frequency deviation of each area in the considered interconnected power system under case A of scenario 1.

Fig. 16. Tie-line power deviation of EPS area with other areas of the studied system (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) Under Case A of Scenario 1.

integral of squared error (ISE). In this case investigation, ACE is the error variable to be minimized. Based on many previous studies for the LFC applications, the ITAE is applied to optimize the gains of the LFC-based PID controllers for the studied four-area interconnected multi-source power system. The ITAE objective function for the optimization problem of four-area interconnected power systems is formulated as given in Eq. (7). Therefore, the proposed RUN optimization technique is utilized to determine the optimal values of the controllers' gains to provide the optimum frequency control efficacy by reducing the objective function ITAE.

$$ITAE = \int_0^{t_{sim}} (|\Delta f_1| + |\Delta f_2| + |\Delta f_3| + |\Delta f_4| + |\Delta P_{tie12}| + |\Delta P_{tie13}| + |\Delta P_{tie14}|) * t dt \quad (7)$$

where Δf_1 represents the frequency deviation at area 1 (i.e., EPS), Δf_2 is frequency deviation at area 2 (i.e., JPS), Δf_3 is frequency deviation at area 3 (i.e., LPS), and Δf_4 is frequency deviation at area 4 (i.e., SPS). While ΔP_{tie12} is the tie-line power variation between Egypt (area 1) and Jordan (area 2), ΔP_{tie13} is the tie-line power variation between Egypt (area 1) and Libya (area 3), ΔP_{tie14} is the tie-line power variation between Egypt (area 1) and Sudan (area 4), and simulation time is represented by t_{sim} .

The constraints of the proposed PID controller parameters are as follows:

$$K_p^{min} \leq K_p \leq K_p^{max} \quad (8)$$

$$K_i^{min} \leq K_i \leq K_i^{max} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 17. Wind and PV power profile used in area 1 (EPS).

Fig. 18. Wind and PV power profile used in area 2 (JPS).

$$K_d^{min} \leq K_d \leq K_d^{max} \tag{10}$$

where K_p^{min} , K_i^{min} , K_d^{min} , K_p^{max} , K_i^{max} , and K_d^{max} are the minimum and maximum values of the PID controller, respectively. In this study, the range of the PID controller parameters is selected as [0, 100].

4. Runge Kutta (RUN) optimizer

The RUN algorithm is an optimization approach that has been advanced by [35]. This approach is a population-based algorithm, and its construction utilizes the fundamentals of the Runge Kutta mathematical approach that is often employed to deal with typical differential equations. The proposed RUN optimizer has two sections, the first is based on a search mechanism while the second mechanism improves the quality of the solution. Fig. 9 shows the RUN Optimizer technique flowchart. The following section provides the major equations as well as

a summary of the algorithm, with a more extensive analysis of RUN available in [35].

A. Initialization

The first step is the initialization of positions of decision variables randomly that are generated by Eq. (11).

$$X_{n,l} = \text{rand} \cdot (U_l - L_l) + L_l \tag{11}$$

where rand refers to a random number ranging from 0 to 1, L_l states the lower bound of l^{th} variable, U_l is the l^{th} variable upper bound, N is the population size, X_n is one of the solutions ($n = 1, 2, \dots, N$), D refers the optimization problem dimension and l stands to a variable in the solution, ($L = 1, 2, \dots, D$).

B. ROOT of search mechanism

The RUN algorithm uses RK4 to identify the search mechanism. Four weighing factors k_1 , k_2 , k_3 , and k_4 are determined in this step.

Updating solutions

In each iteration, the solution's positions are updated using the

Fig. 19. Frequency deviation of each area of the investigated four-area interconnected power system under case B of Scenario 1.

Fig. 20. Tie-line power deviation of area 1 (The EPS) with the other areas of the studied system (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) Under Case B of Scenario 1.

Runge Kutta method. Equation (12) provides the equation to update the positions.

if $rand < 0.5$

(exploration phase)

$$x_{n+1} = (x_c + r \times SF \times g \times x_c) + SF \times SM + \mu \times x_s$$

else

(Exploitation phase)

$$x_{n+1} = (x_m + r \times SF \times g \times x_m) + SF \times SM + \mu \times x_s \quad (12)$$

End

C. Enhancing solution quality

This step seeks to escape from local optima, enhance the acquired solutions, and ensure rapid convergence. This can be accomplished this, three new solutions (x_{new1} , x_{new2} , and x_{new3}) are considered using the next equations.

if $rand < 0.5$

if $w < 1$

$$x_{new2} = (x_{new1} + r.w.(x_{new1} - x_{avg}) + randn)$$

else

$$x_{new2} = (x_{new1} - x_{avg}) + r.w.(x_{new1} - x_{avg}) + randn)$$

end

end (13)

where

$$w = \exp\left(-c\left(\frac{i}{Maxi}\right)\right) \cdot rand(0, 2) \quad (13-1)$$

$$x_{avg} = \left(\frac{X_{r1} + X_{r2} + X_{r3}}{3}\right) \quad (13-2)$$

$$x_{new1} = \beta^* x_{avg} + (1 - \beta) * x_{best} \quad (13-3)$$

if $rand < w$

Table 9
System performance specifications for Scenario 1 with PID controller designed with various optimization techniques.

PID Controller		Case A			Case B		
		MOS (Hz)	MUS (Hz)	T _s (s)	MOS (Hz)	MUS (Hz)	T _s (s)
Δf ₁	RUN (Proposed)	0.00116	0.00007	12	0.00071	0.00036	4
	CDO	0.00117	0.00039	29	0.00099	0.00041	16
	ALO	0.00018	0.00203	35	0.00075	0.00050	28
Δf ₂	RUN (Proposed)	0.00105	0.00160	15	0.00309	0.00077	9
	CDO	0.00333	0.00162	22	0.00329	0.00128	25
	ALO	0.00117	0.00184	12	0.00425	0.00130	54
Δf ₃	RUN (Proposed)	0.00007	0.00100	12	0.00081	0.00090	10
	CDO	0.00074	0.00113	38	0.00088	0.00102	33
	ALO	0.00018	0.00164	30	0.00107	0.00092	66
Δf ₄	RUN (Proposed)	0.00008	0.00102	12	0.00090	0.00088	11
	CDO	0.00077	0.00110	30	0.00066	0.00103	24
	ALO	0.00017	0.00111	51	0.00114	0.00100	34
ΔP _{tie(12)}	RUN (Proposed)	0.00174	0.00020	6	0.00171	0.00063	7
	CDO	0.00184	0.00120	18	0.00172	0.00111	21
	ALO	0.00194	0.00102	32	0.00173	0.00107	42
ΔP _{tie(13)}	RUN (Proposed)	0.00101	0.00082	17	0.00046	0.00079	12
	CDO	0.00112	0.00088	32	0.00046	0.00086	19
	ALO	0.00111	0.00088	34	0.00039	0.00089	36
ΔP _{tie(14)}	RUN (Proposed)	0.00011	0.00077	14	0.00071	0.00029	11
	CDO	0.00050	0.00079	20	0.00072	0.00037	21
	ALO	0.00019	0.00079	37	0.00075	0.00047	37

Fig. 21. Random load variations applied for area 1 (EPS) & area 2 (JPS) Under Case A of Scenario 2.

$$x_{new3} = (x_{new2} - rand \cdot x_{new2}) + SF \cdot (rand \cdot x_{RK} + (v \cdot x_b - x_{new2})) \quad (14)$$

End

The unknowns (i.e., SF, SM, r, etc.) stated in the aforementioned equations can be calculated by using the numbers and formulas needed in [35]. In [35], the RUN optimizer was compared to various contemporary optimization techniques displaying numerous advantages over them including strong exploration and exploitation competencies, usefulness for numerous real-world optimization challenges, requiring the setting of only two control parameters, and minimal sensitivity to changes in control parameter values. Moreover, limited investigations showed that this new optimization technique performed well in optimizing several engineering optimization issues. As a result, this study presents a robust controller for LFC applications that is designed by the RUN algorithm. The flowchart shown in Fig. 9 illustrates the implementation steps of the optimization algorithm used to obtain the optimal controller parameters.

The improved efficiency of the RUN optimizer is validated by comparing it with other existing optimization algorithms, such as the Ant Lion optimizer (ALO) [49] and Chernobyl disaster optimizer (CDO) [50], in the LFC application of the four-area interconnected multi-source power system. When it came to fine-tuning the frequency controller parameters in the studied power system, the RUN algorithm outperformed the other optimization algorithms. The PID controllers' parameters are finely tuned using the discussed algorithms (i.e., RUN, ALO, and CDO algorithms) assuming the subsequent conditions: 1 % step load perturbation (SLP) in area 1 (i.e., the EPS) and area 2 (i.e., the JPS) at time 0 s. Moreover, the optimization algorithm parameters are implemented using 100 iterations along with 30 search agents. Therefore, the optimal controller parameters based on three optimization algorithms are given in Table 8. The convergence curves of the PID controller for various optimization techniques are shown in Fig. 10. According to Table 8 and Fig. 10, the proposed Runge Kutta technique achieved a significantly lower objective function value than the other

Fig. 22. Frequency deviation of each area of the investigated four-area interconnected power system under Case A of Scenario 2.

Fig. 23. Tie-line power deviation of area 1 (The EPS) with the other areas of the studied system (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) under Case A of Scenario 2.

strategies.

5. Performance assessment of the proposed system

5.1. Assessment of the proposed method against existing works

Although the studied interconnected power system is novel and has not been previously presented in the literature, some studies have focused on examining the frequency stability of the EPS as a single-area power system. These studies can serve as a reliable benchmark for comparison. Therefore, in this analysis, we focus on a single power system, the EPS, to make the comparison. To validate the effectiveness of the proposed PID controller based on the RUN algorithm in frequency regulation of the EPS, its performance is compared with that of the PID controller based on the Moth Swarm Optimization algorithm (MSA), as presented in [51]. In this case, the considered EPS with the proposed

controller based on the RUN algorithm is examined using the nominal system parameters provided in Table 2, accounting for fluctuations in RESs and load. Fig. 11 shows the frequency deviation of the EPS with PID controller based on different optimization algorithms. As shown in Fig. 16, the proposed PID controller based on the RUN algorithm significantly enhances the EPS frequency performance, resulting in smaller transient magnitudes compared to the PID controller based on the MSA algorithm. Therefore, the best performance in terms of frequency stability of the EPS is achieved by employing the proposed controller.

5.2. Stability analysis of the proposed control system

The stability of the feedback control system is critical for ensuring reliable operation. Given that RESs are recognized as a significant source of uncertainty in the evaluation of frequency response in modern power

Fig. 24. Frequency deviation of each area of the studied four-area interconnected power system Under Case B of Scenario 2.

Fig. 25. Tie-line power deviation of area EPS over other areas of the studied system (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) Under Case B of Scenario 2.

grids, their impact on LFC efficiency must be carefully considered. The stability study is conducted using maximum sensitivity analysis to assess the trade-off between stability and performance. MATLAB software is employed to derive the transfer function of a real four-area interconnected power system. Additionally, MATLAB is utilized to determine the open loop gain transfer function for the EPS area. The Laplace transform of the *i*th area into the interconnected power system shown in

Fig. 12 as discussed in [10] and [52] is derived as follows:

$$\Delta f_i(s) = Gp_i(s)Gec_i(s)R_i(s) + \Delta PL_i(s)G_L(s) + \Delta P_{tie}(s)G_{tie}(s) \quad (15)$$

Suppose $\Delta PL_i(s) = 0$ and $\Delta P_{tie}(s) = 0$, so Eq. (15) simplifies to the open-loop gain transfer function as follows:

$$\frac{\Delta f_i(s)}{R_i(s)} = Gp_i(s).Gec_i(s) \quad (16)$$

$$Gp_i(s)Gec_i(s) = \frac{-0.1742s^8 - 5.885s^7 - 69.88s^6 - 354s^5 - 800.7s^4 - 690s^3 - 68.06s^2 - 0.6721s}{s^9 + 33.77s^8 + 401s^7 + 2176s^6 + 7249s^5 + 1.601e04s^4 + 1.861e04s^3 + 7537s^2 + 833.9s + 9.398} \quad (17)$$

Table 10
System performance specifications for Scenario 2 with PID controller designed by multiple optimization techniques.

PID Controller		Case A			Case B		
		MOS (Hz)	MUS (Hz)	T _S (s)	MOS (Hz)	MUS (Hz)	T _S (s)
Δf_1	RUN (Proposed)	0.00011	0.00055	9	0.00026	0.00053	12
	CDO	0.00195	0.00075	24	0.00193	0.00189	20
	ALO	0.00033	0.00069	56	0.00028	0.00072	66
Δf_2	RUN (Proposed)	0.00200	0.00270	9	0.00211	0.00267	17
	CDO	0.00587	0.00274	24	0.00571	0.00269	32
	ALO	0.00228	0.00712	41	0.00237	0.00688	52
Δf_3	RUN (Proposed)	0.00047	0.00031	22	0.00069	0.00142	22
	CDO	0.00127	0.00048	40	0.00129	0.00157	47
	ALO	0.00081	0.00159	52	0.00071	0.00155	73
Δf_4	RUN (Proposed)	0.00042	0.00138	19	0.00070	0.00143	28
	CDO	0.00059	0.00156	30	0.00125	0.00157	60
	ALO	0.00043	0.00170	51	0.00073	0.00162	80
$\Delta P_{tie(12)}$	RUN (Proposed)	0.00182	0.00052	11	0.00169	0.00063	17
	CDO	0.00183	0.00114	20	0.00177	0.00074	20
	ALO	0.00192	0.00052	41	0.00179	0.00112	39
$\Delta P_{tie(13)}$	RUN (Proposed)	0.00012	0.00072	16	0.00063	0.00074	11
	CDO	0.00052	0.00079	23	0.00071	0.00079	22
	ALO	0.00012	0.00079	39	0.00076	0.00075	37
$\Delta P_{tie(14)}$	RUN (Proposed)	0.00012	0.00077	18	0.00063	0.00073	19
	CDO	0.00049	0.00078	24	0.00069	0.00075	22
	ALO	0.00019	0.00079	41	0.00075	0.00074	39

Fig. 26. Frequency deviation of the four-area interconnected power system under case A of Scenario 3 (with + 30 % of their nominal values).

Similarly, the open-loop transfer functions for the JPS, LPS, and SPS areas can be evaluated in the same manner. To assess the stability of the closed-loop system, a Bode diagram is presented for the transfer function of the open-loop system across the considered four-area interconnected system. The stability analysis, which includes two cases (with controller and without controller), is presented in Fig. 13. As observed in Fig. 13, the gain margin amplitude is below the zero dB line, indicating that the phase margin is effectively infinite. This demonstrates that the proposed system is stable with both gain and phase margins. The preceding analysis confirms that the proposed control system design is stable, capable of handling system uncertainties with minimal overshoot, and exhibits improved performance.

6. Simulation results and discussion

In this study, different scenarios were performed using MATLAB/SIMULINK to evaluate and validate the performance of optimal PID

controllers for LFC in a real-world, four-area interconnected multi-source power system. The proposed RUN optimization technique is employed to customize the PID controller gains. The controller gains corresponding to the specified ITAE objective function are presented in Table 8 for each optimization algorithm used, including RUN, ALO, and CDO. The efficacy of the PID controller based on the RUN optimizer is compared to that of the PID controllers based on ALO and CDO algorithms under different disturbances and operating conditions as stated below.

6.1. Scenario 1: Evaluating system performance in case of sudden changes in loads

In this scenario, to determine the effectiveness of the recommended PID controller optimized using the RUN method, a 5 % step load increase was applied to area 1 (EPS) at 200 s, followed by an additional 5 % step load increase in area 2 (JPS) at 400 s, as depicted in Fig. 14. This

Fig. 27. Frequency deviation of the studied four-area interconnected power system under case A of Scenario 3 (with -30% of their nominal values).

Fig. 28. Tie-line power deviation of EPS area with other areas of the studied system (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) under case A of Scenario 3 (with + 30 % of their nominal values).

scenario includes two cases of frequency stability investigation of the considered interconnected power system using the proposed PID controller based on the RUN optimizer, whether the RESs are in service or not.

Case A: The system behavior without RESs

The effectiveness of the recommended PID controller using the RUN optimizer is verified by contrasting it with PID controllers based on ALO and CDO algorithms in frequency regulation of the real four-area interconnected power system without RESs in areas 1 and 2. Fig. 15 displays the frequency deviation of each area of the system under study with the recommended PID controllers based on RUN, ALO, and CDO algorithms. Moreover, the tie-line power deviation of the Egypt area with other areas of the studied system (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) is represented in Fig. 16. The outcomes demonstrated that the

recommended PID controller parameter tuned using the RUN algorithm can deliver superior performance compared to PID controllers optimized with the ALO and CDO algorithms when subjected to sudden load changes.

Case B: The system behavior with RESs

The efficiency of the recommended PID controller using RUN optimizer is compared with PID controllers based on ALO as well as CDO algorithms in frequency regulation of the real four-area interconnected power system where RESs are linked to area 1 (EPS) and area 2 (JPS). The recommended PID controller based on the RUN optimizer is verified by taking the wind and solar PV power variations in area 1 (EPS) and area 2 (JPS) into consideration, as indicated in Fig. 17, and Fig. 18, correspondingly. Fig. 19 displays the frequency deviation of the four-area studied system with the recommended PID controllers based on

Fig. 29. Tie-line power deviation of EPS area with other areas of the studied system (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) under case A of Scenario 3 (with -30% of their nominal values).

Fig. 30. Frequency deviation of the investigated four-area interconnected power system under case B of Scenario 3 (with $+30\%$ of their nominal values).

RUN, ALO, and CDO methods. Fig. 20 demonstrates the tie-line power deviation of the EPS area over other areas of the studied system (i.e., JPS, LPS, and SPS). The findings show that the recommended PID controller using the RUN optimizer gives higher performance than other controller designs, with the recommended RUN-based PID controller providing fewer deviations as well as rapid settling times (i.e., enhances all performance metrics) compared to PID controllers based on ALO and CDO algorithms. Table 9 listed system performance specifications with PID controller designed using various optimization techniques in terms of maximum overshoot (MOS), minimum undershoot (MUS) as well as settling time. Moreover, this demonstrates the efficacy and competitiveness of the recommended RUN optimizer in LFC applications over other optimization techniques.

6.2. Scenario 2: Evaluating system performance under random load changes

In this scenario, to assess the performance of the proposed PID controller based on the RUN algorithm, a random load change profile was applied in area 1 (EPS) and area 2 (JPS), as shown in Fig. 21. This scenario includes two cases to analyze the frequency stability of the interconnected power system with the proposed RUN-based PID controller, where RESs are in service and when they are not.

Case A: The system behavior without RESs

In this instance, the validation of the effectiveness of the proposed PID controller utilizing the RUN optimizer is conducted through a comparison with PID controllers employing ALO and CDO algorithms.

Fig. 31. Frequency deviation of the studied four-area interconnected power system under case B of Scenario 3 (with -30% of their nominal values).

Fig. 32. Tie-line power deviation of EPS area with the other areas of the studied system with + 30 % of their nominal values (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) under case B of Scenario 3.

This evaluation focuses on frequency regulation within a genuine four-area interconnected power system, excluding RESs in area 1 and 2. The frequency deviation of each area of the studied system with the proposed PID controllers based on RUN, ALO, and CDO algorithms is shown in Fig. 22. Fig. 23 displays the tie-line power deviation of area 1 (Egypt) with the other areas of the studied system (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan). The findings demonstrate the robustness of the recommended RUN-PID controller and its competent performance according to random load changes.

Case B: The system behavior with RESs

The effectiveness of the recommended PID controller employing the RUN optimizer is tested against PID controllers utilizing ALO and CDO

algorithms for frequency control in a real four-area interconnected power system. This system incorporates RESs in Area 1 (EPS) and Area 2 (JPS). Validation of the proposed PID controller considers changes in wind and solar PV power in both areas (1&2), as depicted in Figs. 17 and 18. Fig. 24 illustrates frequency deviation in the four-area system with PID controllers based on RUN, ALO, and CDO algorithms. Additionally, Fig. 25 demonstrates tie-line power deviation between area 1 (EPS) and other areas (JPS, LPS, and SPS) within the system. The results demonstrate that, in comparison to alternative controllers, the proposed PID controller based on the RUN optimizer performs better. Compared to PID controllers based on ALO and CDO algorithms, the proposed PID controller based on the RUN optimizer provided lower deviations as well

Fig. 33. Tie-line power deviation of EPS area with the other areas of the studied system with -30% of their nominal values (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) under case B of Scenario 3.

Table 11

System performance specifications for Scenario 3 (with $+30\%$ of their nominal values) with PID controller designed using various optimization techniques.

PID Controller		Case A			Case B		
		MOS (Hz)	MUS (Hz)	T_s (s)	MOS (Hz)	MUS (Hz)	T_s (s)
Δf_1	RUN (Proposed)	0.00134	0.00035	19	0.00074	0.00200	8
	CDO	0.00154	0.00069	30	0.00143	0.00204	20
	ALO	0.00143	0.00079	66	0.00079	0.00211	67
Δf_2	RUN (Proposed)	0.00191	0.00084	11	0.00165	0.00508	12
	CDO	0.00463	0.00207	27	0.00434	0.00531	24
	ALO	0.00195	0.00559	43	0.00196	0.00535	41
Δf_3	RUN (Proposed)	0.00034	0.00111	23	0.00040	0.00115	20
	CDO	0.00108	0.00131	45	0.00102	0.00123	46
	ALO	0.00050	0.00119	63	0.00042	0.00124	64
Δf_4	RUN (Proposed)	0.00039	0.00114	38	0.00039	0.00116	20
	CDO	0.00108	0.00130	57	0.00101	0.00121	48
	ALO	0.00041	0.00137	90	0.00046	0.00128	63
$\Delta P_{tie(12)}$	RUN (Proposed)	0.00228	0.00033	20	0.00224	0.00049	13
	CDO	0.00236	0.00160	27	0.00237	0.00152	24
	ALO	0.00246	0.00058	33	0.00243	0.00064	41
$\Delta P_{tie(13)}$	RUN (Proposed)	0.00015	0.00090	15	0.00029	0.00086	19
	CDO	0.00070	0.00093	30	0.00066	0.00087	24
	ALO	0.00020	0.00096	48	0.00033	0.00098	42
$\Delta P_{tie(14)}$	RUN (Proposed)	0.00015	0.00088	19	0.00049	0.00053	21
	CDO	0.00069	0.00090	31	0.00064	0.00086	35
	ALO	0.00025	0.00092	50	0.00060	0.00084	42

as quicker settling times (i.e., more effective values in all performance indices). The numerical results of the transient specification (i.e., MOS, MUS, and T_s) for the three schemes are listed in Table 10. This demonstrates the proposed optimization algorithm’s superiority and efficacy over alternative optimization algorithms in the context of LFC application.

6.3. Scenario 3: Evaluating system performance under random load changes with variations of system parameters (system uncertainties)

To validate the robustness of the recommended RUN-PID controller and its competent performance and to check system uncertainties under random load changes with system parameter variations (i.e., system uncertainties). H and D considered the variable parameters in this study.

Systems with $\pm 30\%$ of their nominal values are tested and simulated. Like before two scenarios—one with RESs on bar and the other off bar—are included in this scenario to ensure the frequency stability of the power system under study with the recommended RUN-based PID controller.

Case A: The system behavior without RESs

This time, a comparison with PID controllers that use the ALO and CDO algorithms is used to verify the efficacy of the suggested PID controller that makes use of the RUN optimizer methodology. With RESs in areas 1 and 2 excluded, this analysis concentrates on a frequency regulation study for a real four-area linked power system. Figs. 26 and 27 show the frequency deviation with $\pm 30\%$ of their nominal values, respectively, with the proposed PID controllers using RUN, ALO, and CDO algorithms for each area of the studied system. The tie-line power

Table 12

System performance specifications for Scenario 3 (with $\pm 30\%$ of their nominal values) with PID controller designed using various optimization techniques.

PID Controller		Case A			Case B		
		MOS (Hz)	MUS (Hz)	T_s (s)	MOS (Hz)	MUS (Hz)	T_s (s)
Δf_1	RUN (Proposed)	0.00155	0.00359	17	0.00168	0.00358	18
	CDO	0.00370	0.00365	28	0.00263	0.00367	20
	ALO	0.00159	0.00378	49	0.00224	0.00375	52
Δf_2	RUN (Proposed)	0.00304	0.00952	10	0.00328	0.00883	18
	CDO	0.00668	0.00941	26	0.00777	0.00938	25
	ALO	0.00813	0.00996	31	0.00395	0.00975	43
Δf_3	RUN (Proposed)	0.00031	0.00190	18	0.00086	0.00129	19
	CDO	0.00171	0.00217	29	0.00168	0.00169	31
	ALO	0.00091	0.00121	49	0.00127	0.00206	53
Δf_4	RUN (Proposed)	0.00077	0.00121	8	0.00073	0.00171	25
	CDO	0.00165	0.00130	12	0.00165	0.00198	41
	ALO	0.00093	0.00135	15	0.00093	0.00221	56
$\Delta P_{tie(12)}$	RUN (Proposed)	0.00233	0.00067	16	0.00373	0.00063	19
	CDO	0.00237	0.00154	25	0.00387	0.00261	22
	ALO	0.00244	0.00068	43	0.00397	0.00088	45
$\Delta P_{tie(13)}$	RUN (Proposed)	0.00016	0.00078	23	0.00038	0.00140	15
	CDO	0.00071	0.00090	37	0.00108	0.00146	22
	ALO	0.00024	0.00096	51	0.00069	0.00154	41
$\Delta P_{tie(14)}$	RUN (Proposed)	0.00015	0.000090	19	0.00026	0.00127	14
	CDO	0.00063	0.00094	30	0.00109	0.00154	25
	ALO	0.00024	0.00096	49	0.00065	0.00140	36

Fig. 34. Real-time implementation setup.

deviation of the Egypt area compared to other areas of the studied system with $\pm 30\%$ of their nominal values (i.e., Jordan, Libya, and Sudan) is displayed in Figs. 28 and 29. The suggested coordinated control approach is a reliable controller that can handle system uncertainties without the need to return its parameters.

Case B: The system behavior with RESs

For frequency control in an actual four-area linked power system, the efficacy of the proposed PID controller using the RUN optimizer is compared to PID controllers using ALO and CDO algorithms. RESs in Area 1 (EPS) and Area 2 (JPS) are incorporated into this system.

Variations in wind and solar PV power are taken into account when validating the proposed PID controller in both locations (1&2). Figs. 30 and 31 illustrate frequency deviation in the four-area system with PID controllers based on RUN, ALO, and CDO algorithms with $\pm 30\%$ of their nominal values, respectively. Additionally, tie-line power deviation between EPS area and others (JPS, LPS, and SPS) within the system with $\pm 30\%$ of their nominal values are demonstrated in Figs. 32 and 33, respectively. The findings demonstrate the superior performance of the suggested PID controller based on the RUN optimizer over other controllers. In contrast to PID controllers that utilize ALO and CDO

Fig. 35. OPAL-RT real-time validation results: frequency deviation of the investigated four-area interconnected power system without RESs.

Fig. 36. OPAL-RT real-time validation results: Tie-line power deviation of EPS area with the other areas of the studied system without RESs.

algorithms, better values across all performance indices were obtained by the recommended PID controller, which was based on the RUN optimizer and offered smaller variances and faster settling times. This indicates that, in the context of LFC application, the suggested optimization technique is more effective and successful than other optimization algorithms. Tables 11 and 12 display the transient specifications of the system, such as MOS, MUS, and TS, for Scenario 3 with system parameters variation by $\pm 30\%$ of their nominal values, respectively. From the last two figures, it is clear from the computational findings of the transient specification that the system response utilizing the recommended control approach is quicker, has a fewer steady-state error, and is better damped compared to others.

6.4. Scenario 4: real-time implementation

This section presents the real-time implementation used to evaluate the feasibility of the proposed PID controllers based on the RUN algorithm within the examined real four-area interconnected power system. This evaluation is essential for assessing the controllers' effectiveness in managing and optimizing the interconnected power system performance under real-world conditions. Therefore, the proposed technique under investigation is tested and verified experimentally using the real-time system OPA-RT (OP4610) platform on the studied real four-area interconnected power system. Fig. 34 depicts the real-time implementation framework for the proposed PID controller within the studied interconnected power system. It showcases the system architecture, highlighting the integration of essential components, including OPAL-RT and

Fig. 37. OPAL-RT real-time validation results: frequency deviation of the investigated four-area interconnected power system including RESs.

Fig. 38. OPAL-RT real-time validation results: Tie-line power deviation of EPS area with the other areas of the studied system including RESs.

a laptop, to ensure effective testing and validation of the control strategy.

In this setup, the laptop serves as the host computer for creating, deploying, and monitoring control algorithms. It directly interfaces with the OPAL-RT (OP4610) system, enabling rapid transfer of control code, continuous acquisition of real-time data, and visualizing the interconnected power system performance in real-time. Moreover, its robust processing capabilities and ample storage support detailed data logging and subsequent in-depth analysis. An Ethernet cable is essential for establishing connections and ensuring reliable data transfer between the laptop, accessories, and the OPAL-RT interface, minimizing the risk of interruptions during testing. The OPAL-RT real-time simulation facilitates the execution of the power system model integrated with the proposed controller, enabling rigorous performance evaluation. With a high-speed discrete-time operation at 0.1 μs intervals, the simulation

accurately replicates real-world system dynamics, providing a reliable and precise platform for controller validation. This scenario examines two distinct cases, the power system with and without RESs, to rigorously assess the effectiveness of the proposed controller in a real-time implementation.

Case A: The system behavior without RESs

As illustrated in Fig. 34, real-time implementation using the OPAL-RT is performed to validate the feasibility and practical implementation of the proposed controller. Throughout the real-time implementation, the power system operates with a sampling time of 0.1 μs to ensure high-precision evaluation. The dynamic real-time response of the system considered for Scenario 1, Case A (which characterized by a sudden load change), is depicted in Figs. 35 and 36. Fig. 35 shows the frequency deviation of the investigated four-area interconnected power system without RESs under a real-time implementation environment. While

dynamic real-time response of the tie-line power deviation of the EPS-area with the other areas of the studied system without RESs is shown in Fig. 36. The real-time results confirm the robustness and practical feasibility of the proposed control technique.

Case B: The system behavior with RESs

In this case, the real-time implementation of the investigated power system with the proposed controller is carried out under the same conditions as in Scenario 1, Case B, which involves applying a sudden load change and integrating RESs. The dynamic real-time response of the frequency deviation of the investigated four-area interconnected power system including RESs is shown in Fig. 37. Fig. 38 shows the tie-line power deviation of the EPS-area with the other areas of the studied system including RESs, under a real-time implementation environment. Figs. 37 and 38 highlight the robustness of the proposed PID controller in handling disturbances caused by fluctuations in RESs and load variations.

7. Conclusion and future work

This paper discusses the frequency stability of a real four-area interconnected multi-source power system incorporated with non-inertia sources such as wind farms and solar PV that affect power system stability. The proposed PID controller was optimally tuned using the RUN optimization algorithm to obtain the most effective parameter keeping the system under study more stable during abnormalities due to RENs or load disturbances. Moreover, the efficiency of the PID controller tuned by utilizing the RUN optimizer is compared to PID controllers optimized with other computational evolutionary algorithms such as Ant Lion Optimizer (ALO) and Chernobyl Disaster Optimizer (CDO). The outcomes demonstrated that even when RESs are incorporated into the interconnected power system, the recommended RUN-based PID controller maintains high-frequency stability. Moreover, the RUN optimizer was found to be more effective than the ALO and CDO optimization algorithms in LFC applications under diverse operation scenarios and power system disturbances. Also, it is clear from the results obtained that the system enters steady-state instances approximately 15 s faster. The findings reveal that the proposed controller is effective in improving the MOS by roughly 20 % and advancing the MUS by nearly 30 %. Moreover, the practicality and effectiveness of the proposed controller were experimentally validated through real-time implementation using the OPAL-RT platform. The impact of various energy storage systems on frequency stabilization in real interconnected power systems will be explored in future work to address the significant fluctuations in renewable energy generation and load variations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Diaa M. Gawad: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gaber Magdy:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **M.A. Ebrahim:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Eduard Petlenkov:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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